

Stiffness Perception with Delayed Visual Feedback in Unimanual and Bimanual Interactions

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Abstract. During interactions with elastic objects, we integrate haptic and visual information to create the perception of stiffness. Previous studies of stiffness perception with delayed visual feedback focused on vertical, right-hand interactions. Due to the diverse nature of our interactions with objects, we aimed to study the effect of visual delay on stiffness perception during horizontal movements in unimanual and bimanual interactions. We designed two psychophysical experiments, with horizontal unimanual and horizontal bimanual interactions with elastic objects with different levels of visual delay. In both experiments, consistently with previous studies, visual delay caused overestimation of stiffness that scaled linearly with the size of the delay. During bimanual but not unimanual interactions, the sensitivity of participants to small differences in stiffness increased. This suggests that participants improved their sensitivity by integrating information acquired by both hands. These findings carry significant implications for the design of visual-haptic interfaces and the development of bilateral bimanual controllers.

Keywords: Bimanual Interaction · Stiffness perception · Visual Delay .

1 Introduction

In daily interactions, our central nervous system integrates visual and haptic information to form stiffness perception, such as when selecting ripe fruit or detecting tumors during surgery. A delay between visual and haptic feedback, common in VR and teleoperation, can distort stiffness perception. For example, delayed visual feedback causes overestimation of stiffness, and the effect increases with the size of the visual delay [1]. However, the effect of visual delay was studied to date during unimanual vertical interactions. While this is an excellent starting point, our daily interactions often involve movements in various directions and with both hands. Therefore, we aimed to bridge this gap in knowledge by examining the impact of visual delay on stiffness perception during horizontal unimanual and bimanual interactions with virtual elastic objects.

2 Methods

We perform two experiments in which participants looked at an LCD screen (60Hz refresh rate) via a semi-silvered mirror. In experiment 1, 9 right-handed participants held a Geomagic TouchX haptic device that rendered virtual elastic objects. Participants could

freely move the haptic device but they felt a force feedback only along the horizontal rightward-leftward axis (Fig. 1(a)) according to:

$$f_R(t) = \begin{cases} -k(x(t) - x_0), & \text{if } x < x_0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where x_0 is the virtual object's boundary and $x(t)$ is the haptic device's end-effector position. They compared a standard object ($k=85$ [N/m]) to eight comparison objects with stiffness levels ranging from 40 to 130 [N/m]. The standard object had one of three visual delays: 0, 50, and 100 [msec], and the visual feedback of the comparison objects was never delayed. At the end of each trial, participants reported which object felt stiffer. Each experiment had 200 trials: 8 for familiarization and 192 for data analysis.

In experiment 2, 14 right-handed participants held two haptic devices, one at each hand. The protocol mirrored experiment 1, but they interacted with each object with both hands. Effectively, they interacted with 2 identical elastic objects conjoined by an orange wall in the middle, allowing for simultaneous probing with each hand but without transmission of interaction forces between the hands via the object (Fig. 1(b)).

Based on participant responses, we determined the probability of perceiving that the comparison object had a higher level of stiffness as a function of the difference in stiffness levels between the comparison and standard objects. For each delay condition we fitted logistic psychometric curve. From each curve we extracted the point of subjective equality (PSE) and the just noticeable difference (JND) [2]. Additionally, in our statistical analysis, for each experiment, we fitted two one-way repeated measures ANOVA models with normally distributed PSE and JND as dependent variables and the visual delay as independent factor .

3 Results

We observed that in both unimanual and bimanual interactions, the introduction of visual delay resulted in a rightward shift of the psychometric curve, as shown in (Fig. 2(a)), indicating a positive PSE and an overestimation of stiffness due to the visual delay. Furthermore, as the visual delay increased, the PSE increased for unimanual (Fig. 2(b)) and bimanual (Fig. 2(c)) interactions. Moreover, during unimanual interaction the JND increased with visual delay (Fig. 2(d)), and the JND remained consistent ($F_{2,26} = 0.57, p = 0.58$) across all conditions during bimanual interaction (Fig. 2(e)).

Fig. 1. Experimental setups for unimanual (a) and bimanual (b) interactions.

Fig. 2. (a) Psychometric curves fitted to participant responses for the three conditions. (b)-(c) and (d)-(e) show unimanual and bimanual PSE and JND values, respectively. Bars represent the mean PSE and JND for the three conditions. Data markers indicate individual participant responses, with gray lines connecting each participant's PSE/JND values. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001.

4 Discussion

In both interactions, we observed the same trend: the introduction of visual delay led to an overestimation of stiffness. Furthermore, this overestimation scaled linearly with the size of delay – the larger the delay was the harder the objects were perceived. During horizontal unimanual interactions, stiffness discrimination sensitivity decreased with increasing visual delay, consistent with prior research but more pronounced. This could be due to the differing interaction dynamics: vertical interactions involve force along one axis, while horizontal interactions involve conflicting forces along two axes – gravity and the elastic object, potentially causing more confusion. In contrast, during bimanual interactions, JND values remained constant with visual delay. This observation suggests that adding information from the left hand in the interaction enhanced participants' sensitivity to subtle variations in stiffness levels, resulting in higher precision compared to unimanual interaction. We hope our findings will contribute to enhancing bilateral bimanual controllers across various systems, particularly in practical applications like robot-assisted minimally invasive surgery (RAMIS), where surgeons rely on both hands.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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